

DARIAH-EU

Digital Research Infrastructure
for the Arts and Humanities

DARIAH-ERIC: ANNUAL REPORT 2015

Front page image:

Venue of DARIAH's General Assembly meeting in 2015 - Germany's
Federal Ministry of Education and Research, Berlin.

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In August 2014 DARIAH-EU entered a completely new phase by being founded anew as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). First added to the ESFRI Roadmap in 2006, and having successfully navigated its preparatory and transitional phases, DARIAH has the aim now of being fully operational by 2019. This significant transition was achieved thanks to the enormous energy and effort of our founding members. With an established lifetime of 20 years, our vision becomes long-term. Now is the time for considered renewal while building on the proven project and programme outputs achieved with our members, partners and associates, welded together through joint activity since 2006, when we first appeared on the ESFRI Roadmap. The DARIAH network has also matured over this time - its depth of experience and knowledge in cooperation across disciplines, technical domains and member countries provide the incubator for truly applied innovation. DARIAH is here to have a transformational effect on the humanities – but we must also seek to be in tune with and gain impetus for our research domains from changes in the broader digital society over the past decade. In this way, the Digital Humanities and digital scholarship gain relevance both in terms of advancing research and in terms of innovation for creative and arts industries.

Welcome to DARIAH!

Jacques Dubucs
Chair, DARIAH General Assembly

Laurent Romary
President, DARIAH Board of Directors

DARIAH's unique ethos is "by researchers, for researchers". Our great strength lies therefore in our natural appeal to those who are at the cutting edge of new research in the humanities, based on our community-driven agenda. We are therefore naturally able to support, inspire and connect a multitude of forward-looking scholarly networks across the arts and humanities. DARIAH is also very dynamic. In an era of great change, given the digital turn also in the academy, for researchers to be able to lead transformations in new technology-driven methods and forms of publication is crucial. This aspect is now as much part of the humanities researcher's activity as impact metrics, public engagement, teaching and research ethics. However, with the relevant technology becoming increasingly a commodity, humanities scholars require more than ever before new skills and competences, in order to enjoy new such digitally-enabled research opportunities to their fullest. People and skills are our most valuable infrastructure.

In this first full year after our founding as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium in the autumn of 2014, our main focus has been threefold: to establish the DARIAH Coordination Office, build operational sustainability and extend our network of Members and Cooperating Partners. By September 2015, we had a fully-staffed support office operating out of three sites across Europe and had begun to implement a large-scale H2020-funded project, called Humanities at Scale (HaS), to embed our future capacity. By November we had already welcomed two further Members and six Cooperating Partners.

We would not have reached these three major milestones without the huge amount of support and expertise we have been able to draw on from our membership and our highly committed governing bodies. I would like to express my sincere thanks to all in DARIAH who have put us firmly as an ERIC on the road to help realise the long-term transformation of arts and humanities scholarship throughout Europe.

Mike Mertens,
DARIAH CEO

Organisation Overview

DARIAH-EU is a pan-European and cooperative infrastructure for the digitally-enabled arts and humanities. Its work is shaped, informed and carried out by the organisations in its national member consortia, its Cooperating Partners and through DARIAH-led and several affiliated projects.

The following gives an overview over the most important bodies and concepts related to DARIAH-EU's work.

Members

DARIAH-EU currently has 17 members, which are member countries of the European Union. More information on our individual members is available, below, in Annex 1

General Assembly (GA)

The GA is the governing body of DARIAH. It decides, for example, to accept new Members, approves financial reports and the annual activity report. Each Member country is represented in the DARIAH General Assembly. More information on the National Representatives is available in Annex 3.

Board of Directors (BoD)

DARIAH-EU has three part-time directors. Together they are responsible for the overall strategic direction of DARIAH, in consultation with the General Assembly and the Senior Management Team. The Board is supported by the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office.

Senior Management Team (SMT)

The Board of Directors consults the SMT on all general matters. The SMT is composed of the Chair and the Vice-Chair of the National Coordinators Committee, as well as the Chair and Vice-Chair of the Joint Research Committee. In addition the Chair of the Scientific Board and the relevant officers of the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office attend Senior Management Team meetings.

Scientific Board

The Scientific Board advises DARIAH on scientific and technical matters. Its members are arts and humanities researchers with significant experience in digitally enabled research methods.

DARIAH Coordination Office (DCO)

The daily work of DARIAH-EU is undertaken by the DCO, it is responsible for finance, coordination and communications.

National Coordinators Committee (NCC)

Each DARIAH Member Country has its own National Coordinator, who coordinates DARIAH activities in his or her country. In the NCC they meet regularly to integrate their national DARIAH activities at the European level.

Joint Research Committee (JRC)

The JRC organises the scientific and technical integration of DARIAH activities. It is chaired by DARIAH's Chief Integration Officer (CIO) and consists of the Heads of each of DARIAH's Virtual Competency Centres.

Virtual Competency Centers

In order to develop, curate and maintain resources and services, DARIAH relies on Virtual Competency Centres (VCC) and working groups. The VCCs coordinate the Working Groups and define general topics under which they work:

- VCC 1: **e-Infrastructure** – To develop and implement a shared technology platform for arts and humanities research.
- VCC 2: **Research and Education Liaison** – To investigate and embed new ways of sharing researcher’s knowledge, methodologies and expertise.
- VCC 3: **Scholarly Content Management** – To diversify the exposure and dissemination of scholarly content.
- VCC 4: **Advocacy, Impact and Outreach** – To interface with key influencers in and for the arts and humanities, including beyond the academy.

Working Groups

In these groups researchers from all DARIAH-EU partners share their expertise and work together to deliver services for the community to build up and expand existing infrastructure. These services can be scholarly, technical, editorial or organisational. In the period 2014-2015, the working groups in DARIAH were repositioned to become more central to our operations as well as being the opportunity for building stronger researcher networks. In 2015, the following groups were fully constituted and defined by and for the community after approval by the Joint Research Committee and the Senior Management Team:

List of approved working groups in 2015:

Analysing and Linking Biographical Data
Certification and Trustworthiness of Repositories
Community Engagement
Digital Annotation
Digital Methods and Practices Observatory (DiM-PO)
Guidelines and Standards (GiSt)
Image Science and Media Art Research
Impact Factors and Success Criteria
Lexical Resources
MESO, Mediaevalist’s Sources
Meta-Registry – An Integrated Registry Service

Text and Data Analytics
Thesaurus Maintenance
Training and Education
Visual Media for Digital Humanities

Cooperating Partners

Organisations from non-members countries can also work with DARIAH-EU. This is currently the case with Switzerland, the United Kingdom and Sweden. Cooperating Partners commit to working within and through our Working Groups for a period of two years. Cooperating Partners have the same access to DARIAH resources as Members and Observers but may not determine policy or be represented in the General Assembly, DARIAH’s governing and executive body.

Affiliates

DARIAH-EU is closely cooperating with several affiliated projects. DARIAH in many cases provides the necessary infrastructure, skills or expertise to ensure an effective execution of European research programmes and projects in the digitally-enabled arts and humanities.

High-Level Principles & Strategic Directions

In light of our founding as an ERIC, starting in 2014 but continuing into 2015, we began to devise some guiding high-level principles. These principles are intended to allow both researchers and those who support them to orientate themselves regarding what DARIAH is ambitious to achieve, while respecting the conditions of transformation for the arts and humanities, from analogue to digital, from national to international, from digital humanists to all those in the humanities that work in a digitally-enabled way. The principles are as follows:

- **Community-driven** – DARIAH activities and services should be driven by humanities researchers, and need to be performed by humanities researchers where possible.
- **Integrate existing resources** – DARIAH will reuse existing resources and facilitate their integration, since this ensures that the infrastructure efficiently captures the work of humanities communities.
- **Promote digital methods** – DARIAH should promote digital methods where possible, to ensure sustainable digital humanities. Where analogue data is still essential, its digital representation or metadata should enable discovery.
- **DARIAH is an open infrastructure** – DARIAH provides seamless access to data and services, independent from the national or institutional origin of researchers. This will mean that the DARIAH infrastructure fundamentally supports the concerns of humanities researchers per se, wherever they are.
- **DARIAH is a trustworthy infrastructure** – Resources and services within DARIAH are trustworthy. All components of the infrastructure need to be trustworthy: partners, services, resources and procedures.

Administrative, Legal & Regulatory

DARIAH in this period, having opened a bank account in 2014 in France, in light of this being the formal seat of the new ERIC, also embedded a workflow and confirmed its system for determining the nominal value of the national in-kind contributions and the absolute value of financial contributions of its members, based on a progressive mapping of relative GDP. Given DARIAH's aim to develop a critical mass of tools, services, training and code that can be shared and utilized across borders by researcher communities, related partners in cultural

heritage and the public, the emphasis has been on in-kind contributions, which equals 90% of the contribution. In 2015, our Members in-kind contributions exceeded however even the projected value by 350%. DARIAH also began in the autumn to set out a plan to refine the workflows for collecting, describing and categorising in-kind contributions. This was done in part in preparation for practical work to implement a new catalogue of our collective tools and services under the Humanities at Scale (HaS) project (cp. Annex 5).

Education and Training

For DARIAH, as an infrastructure that stresses the human as much as the information network, the education and training of future generations of researchers in the new methods, tools and collaborative research environments that mark the digitally-enabled arts and humanities are critical. Hence DARIAH has partnered with Erasmus+ to develop #dariahTeach and a DH Course Registry of European university qualifications that address the digital humanities.

#dariahTeach

#dariahTeach develops open-source, high quality, multilingual teaching materials for the digital arts and humanities. Begun in January 2015 and running through June 2017, #dariahTeach is funded through an Erasmus+ Strategic Partnership Grant. Its goal is to strengthen alliances and foster innovative teaching and learning practices among members of the DARIAH network. This Strategic Partnership is under the lead of Maynooth University, with seven other participating institutions: Aarhus University's DIGHUMLAB (Denmark), "Athena" Research Center (Greece), the Austrian Academy of Sciences (Austria), Belgrade Centre for Digital Humanities (Serbia), Erasmus University Rotterdam (The Netherlands) and University of Lausanne and the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (Switzerland). The partners represent countries that are either

founding DARIAH countries or are working towards to become members, and exemplify a depth of experience within the digital arts and humanities field across Europe .

#dariahTeach is a project of DARIAH's VCC2: Research and Education. VCC2 promotes and supports the use of research data and ICT methods and technologies. It acts as the primary contact with the arts and humanities research and teaching communities, providing the interface between DARIAH and researchers undertaking basic, applied and practice-led research. In 2015 VCC2 Research and Education was coordinated by Susan Schreibman (Maynooth University, Ireland) and Marianne Ping Huang (Vice-Dean, Aarhus University, Denmark).

Digital Humanities Course Registry

The course registry was created by a consortium of DARIAH Virtual Competency Centre 2, Erasmus University, Rotterdam, the University of Cologne, with credits to the University of Paris.

The DH Course Registry is a collaborative inventory of DH courses in Europe. It links educational efforts on the interaction between humanities and information technology. The main objective of this resource is to help students, researchers, lecturers and institutions to find, add and connect to courses or programmes in the digital humanities field. Furthermore, it allows academic institutions to improve the visibility of their courses and study programmes

Figure 1:
DARIAH's Course Registry lists European Digital Humanities courses: <https://dh-registry.de.dariah.eu/>

The screenshot shows the 'Digital Humanities Course Registry' website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the DARIAH-EU logo and the title 'Digital Humanities Course Registry'. Below the navigation bar is a map of Europe with red pins indicating the locations of various courses. The map shows pins for Ireland, Spain, Portugal, France, Italy, Germany, Poland, Denmark, Norway, Sweden, and Finland. Below the map is a table of courses with columns for Course Name, Type, University, Department, Information, and Curriculum. The table lists three courses: 'Digital Heritage' (Degree: Master, University of York, Archaeology), 'First Level Master in Digital Humanities' (Degree: Master, Università Ca' Foscari, Department of Humanities), and 'European Heritage, Digital Media and the Information Society (EuroMACHS)' (Degree: Master, Karl-Franzens-Universität Graz, Geisteswissenschaftliche Fakultät). At the bottom of the page, there is a footer with the text 'ANNUAL REPORT 2015' and 'Ausg. 9'.

Course Name	Type	University	Department	Information	Curriculum
Digital Heritage	Degree: Master	University of York	Archaeology	Link >>	-
First Level Master in Digital Humanities	Degree: Master	Università Ca' Foscari	Department of Humanities	Link >>	-
European Heritage, Digital Media and the Information Society (EuroMACHS)	Degree: Master	Karl-Franzens-Universität Graz	Geisteswissenschaftliche Fakultät	Link >>	-

Marketing and Communications

In the course of 2015, the focus of our work in this area has been on establishing and refining communications networks between the now three offices in DARIAH-ERIC, in Berlin, Goettingen and The Hague. With the start of the Humanities at Scale project, funded by Horizon 2020, new formal channels of communication were also set up, to ensure regular updates, ease of project management and information flows. Chief amongst these developments has been the adoption of an open, secure and platform-agnostic videoconferencing tool, Web-based collaboration tools, a dedicated website for the Humanities at Scale project and a new dedicated DARIAH Newsletter. Given that the Communications Officer was only employed in May, and its commencement was in September, further specific materials will be developed in 2016. In addition, mutual lines of communication have been established with our associated partners PARTHENOS and EHRI, as well as with CLARIN-ERIC, for reciprocal reinforcement of our impact on the collective domain of computer-assisted and data-driven humanities.

DARIAH Theme – “Open Humanities”

Since 2015 DARIAH-EU’s Board of Directors sets an annual thematic priority, the DARIAH Theme. The idea is to stimulate activities and events related to a topic important to digitally enabled research in the arts and humanities.

The DARIAH theme “Open Humanities” was launched in early 2015. DARIAH decided on making open humanities a priority for DARIAH, because to date arts and humanities data resources are not easily available. In many cases, they are locked away or isolated in many other ways. Most likely, the resources will be owned by different communities and subject to different rights. DARIAH is committed to changing this situation and thus promotes open arts and humanities research. It works towards an effective use of data resources, also by

communities who do not yet have digital arts and humanities capacities.

DARIAH allocated 45.000 Euros for events exploring the Open Humanities theme, for example, larger conferences, a series of workshops or hackathons.

Requirements

All DARIAH Partner Institutions were invited to send in proposals to organize such events. There were two very important conditions: All theme related activities had to involve more than one DARIAH Member and at least one outside organization.

Outcomes

The Call was published in early 2015. Two peer reviewers reviewed each proposal. In total DARIAH received ten submissions, and decided to fund six projects. They received funding in the range of EUR 5,000 up to EUR 10,000.

Funded projects collaborating with GLAMs:

- DARIAH-DK (Marianne Huang) with the British Library and other institutions: *„Internet of Cultural Things“*.
- DARIAH-Be (Veerle Vanden Daelen) with archives: *„Open History – Sustainable digital publishing of archival catalogues: a workshop for archivists of twentieth-century history archives“*.
- DARIAH-Cy (Marinos Ioannides) and DARIAH-Malta (Milena Dobрева) and Heritage Institutions: *„The e-documentation of the European Intangible Heritage“*.

Funded projects collaborating with universities and publishers:

- DARIAH-RS (Toma Tasovac) and various universities: *„Developing Open Source Training Materials in the Humanities“*
- DARIAH-AT (Eveline Wandl-Vogt) and DARIAH-IE (Alexander O’Connor) with Open Knowledge Foundation and Wikimedia: *„Linked Open Data 4 Living Organisms“*
- DARIAH-IT (Hansmichael Hohenegger) with publishers and museums: *„Models for Open Access Publishing“*

Major Meetings

VCC\All Hands

5th General VCC meeting, Ljubljana, 22-24 April 2015

The 5th General Virtual Competency Centre (VCC) meeting was held in Ljubljana, Slovenia, on 22-24 April 2015 supported by the Slovenian Ministry of Education, Science and Sport. The local hosts, the Virtual Competency Centres and DARIAH-EU worked together to devise a programme that focused on an exchange of knowledge between working groups, many of them only newly established. A particular focus was on working group progress in building up digital services for the broader humanities research community. Additionally, the work carried out in DARIAH's various European affiliated projects was evaluated in terms of the real infrastructural components that will be sustained within the DARIAH network. The meeting overall was organized as an unconference focusing on five thematic parallel sessions: Access, Interoperability, Sustainability, Impact, and Training.

General Assembly

Two meetings of the DARIAH General Assembly were held in the year; the first a virtual one, 05 May, the second face-to-face in conjunction with our other major governance bodies in Berlin, 06 November. The first meeting approved some revisions to the Statutes, including the conditions of Observer status, the appointment of the Scientific Board and accepting six new Cooperating Partners, from Switzerland.

During the second meeting, we had the great pleasure to welcome two new members, Poland and Portugal, thus greatly strengthening the organisation as a whole, adding to the significant expertise and service portfolios of our 15 founding members. In addition, the General Assembly considered a proposal to devise key performance indicators, evaluated the Internal Rules of Procedure, and approved the budget for 2016.

Figure 2:

Alongside the General Assembly DARIAH's Scientific Board gathered for the first time. From left to right: Andrew Prescott, Jacques Dubucs (GA Chair), Patrik Svensson, Riccardo Pozzo, Roxanne Wyns, Jane Ohlmeyer, Chad Gaffield, Manfred Thaller

Annex 1: Member Institutions Overview 2015

MEMBER	NATIONAL COORDINATING INSTITUTION
Austria	Austrian Academy of Sciences
Belgium	Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities (University of Ghent)
Croatia	Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research
Cyprus	Cyprus University of Technology
Denmark	DIGHUMLAB
France	Huma--Num
Germany	University of Göttingen (Göttingen State and University Library)
Greece	Academy of Athens
Ireland	National University of Ireland Maynooth
Italy	Italian National Research Council (NRC)
Luxembourg	Centre Virtuel de la Connaissance sur l'Europe
Malta	Malta Libraries Council
Netherlands	International Institute of Social History
Poland	University of Warsaw
Portugal	National Research Infrastructure ROSSIO
Serbia	Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities
Slovenia	Institute of Contemporary History

Figure 3:
Members of the
DARIAH-ERIC

Annex 2: Cooperating Partners Overview 2015

Sweden	Linnaeus University
Switzerland	University of Basel
	University of Bern
	University of Geneva
	University of Lausanne
	University of Zurich
	Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences
United Kingdom	Glasgow University
	King's College London
	Swansea University

Annex 3: National Representatives in the General Assembly 2015

Austria	Federal Ministry of Science, Research and Economy	Ursula Brustmann
Belgium	Belgian Science Policy Office	Chris De Loof
Croatia	Ministry of Science, Education and Sport	Stasa Skenzic
Cyprus	Cyprus University of Technology	Marinos Ioannides
Denmark	Danish Agency for Science, Technology and Innovation – Ministry of Higher Education and Science	Katinka Stenbjørn
France	Ministère de l'Éducation nationale, de l'Enseignement supérieur et de la Recherche	Jaques Dubucs
Germany	Federal Ministry of Education and Research	Klaus Schindel
Greece	Academy of Athens	Helen Katsiadakis
Ireland	Irish Research Council	Eucharía Meehan
Italy	National Research Council of Italy	Lino Leonardi
Luxembourg	Ministry for Higher Education and Research	Robert Kerger
Malta	Malta Libraries Council	Milena Dobrova
Netherlands	Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research	Alice Dijkstra
Poland	Ministry of Science and Higher Education	Dariusz Drewniak
Portugal		NN
Serbia	National Library of Serbia	Tamara Butigan-Vučaj
Slovenia	Ministry of Education, Science and Sport	Albin Kralj

Annex 4: National Coordinators Committee 2015

Austria	Austrian Academy of Sciences	Charly Moerth
Belgium	University of Ghent	Christophe Verbruggen
Croatia	Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research	Koraljka Kuzman Slogar
Cyprus	Cyprus University of Technology	Marinos Ioannides
Denmark	DIGHUMLAB - DK	Birte Christensen-Dalsgaard
France	Huma-Num (CNRS)	Olivier Baude
Germany	University of Göttingen	Heike Neuroth
Greece	Academy of Athens	Helen Katsiadakis
Ireland	National University of Ireland Maynooth	Susan Schreibman
Italy	National Research Council of Italy	Luca Pezzati
Luxembourg	Centre Virtuel de la Connaissance sur l'Europe	Marianne Backes
Malta	Malta Libraries Council	Milena Dobrevá
Netherlands	International Institute of Social History	Henk Wals
Serbia	Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities	Toma Tasovac
Slovenia	Institute of Contemporary History	Jurij Hadalin

Annex 5: Affiliated Projects and Partners in 2015

Since becoming an ERIC in 2014, DARIAH is increasingly involved in European funded projects addressing topics related to research infrastructures. DARIAH participates directly in two projects, and offers its support and knowledge in several affiliated projects. The list below gives a general overview of European projects in which DARIAH is involved.

HaS-DARIAH

FACTSHEET	
FULL PROJECT NAME	Humanities at Scale: Evolving the DARIAH-ERIC
DURATION	2 years, from September 2015 to August 2017
CONSORTIUM	DARIAH-ERIC (project coordinator), CNRS, DANS, University of Göttingen. CNR, Centre Virtuel de la Connaissance sur l'Europe, Academy of Athens, Austrian Academy of Sciences, Maynooth University, University of Aarhus, Institute of Ethnology and Folklore, Fachhochschule Potsdam.
EU CONTRIBUTION	EUR 1 930 139
CALL FOR PROPOSAL	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1 – HORIZON 2020
WEBSITE	http://has.dariah.eu/

ACTIVITIES

The project **Humanities at Scale** officially started in September 2015. The project is dedicated to enhance the DARIAH-ERIC. It focuses on delivering a stronger core for DARIAH’s operations as well as on providing more resources for all communities within DARIAH. This project will add essential services to DARIAH by enhancing its user community and with a wide range of innovation and training activities. HaS proposes to accelerate the implementation and to strengthen and consolidate DARIAH in the following areas:

- Growing the DARIAH community, by creating hubs in regions not yet part of DARIAH, developing an ambassador programme for Digital Humanities and alternative funding models. HaS

DARIAH offers also an extensive training programme.

- Developing core services: “Humanities at Scale” will better integrate the existing contributions from DARIAH member states and will make its complex model of national contributions more accessible as a whole.
- Informing research communities: Information plays a crucial role within the “Humanities at Scale” project. HaS will disseminate results to relevant academic, cultural, industrial communities and the interested public through publications, presentations and online media.

The project officially started the 1st of September 2015. The first phase of the project has been devoted to the integration of several DARIAH national coordinators after the publication of a call of interest, enabling the consortium to grow in number and in expertise. The first meeting of the project was held in Berlin the 4th of November 2015 and it has represented the occasion to plan the initial phase

of the work. The official Humanities at Scale Kick Off meeting was held in The Hague in January 2016. The two day event was hosted by DANS (Data Archiving and Networked Services). It featured general presentations of the HaS work packages as well as specific workshops on the different HaS activities, and helped to prepare the activities of 2016.

EUROPEANA DSI

FACTSHEET	
FULL PROJECT NAME	EUROPEANA Digital Service Infrastructure
DURATION	14 months, from April 2015 to June 2016
PROJECT COORDINATOR	EUROPEANA FOUNDATION
CONSORTIUM	26 partners from 12 EU countries
EU CONTRIBUTION	EUR 8 900 000
CALL FOR PROPOSAL	Connecting Europe Facility (CEF)
WEBSITE	http://pro.europeana.eu/project/europeana-dsi

ACTIVITIES

EUROPEANA DSI is a project funded under the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) Trans-European Telecommunications Networks Work Programme 2014, in order to develop EUROPEANA as a Digital Service Infrastructure. The core objectives of the EUROPEANA DSI are to innovate the aggregation infrastructure, improve the quality of metadata and the quantity of digital objects available, boost the distribution infrastructure and work towards long-term financial stability through business model innovation.

The project started its operations in 2015, the kick-off meeting took place at the National Archives (NA) and National Library of the Netherlands (KB) in The Hague (19-20 May).

DARIAH participates in WP 3, Re-user services. DARIAH promotes the Europeana API to the digital humanities community and communicates EUROPEANA via its centrally sponsored activities as well as through the various digital humanities classes that are organised through the VCC2, the Digital Humanities Course Registry, through the talks and presentations given during workshops and events (e.g. Electronic Information for Libraries, Riga, 13 November, 2015) and also by working with raising even greater awareness of Europeana Research amongst and via the DARIAH Working Groups.

PARTHENOS

PARTHENOS

Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools
for Heritage E-research Networking,
Optimization and Synergies

FACTSHEET	
FULL PROJECT NAME	Pooling Activities, Resources, and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies.
DURATION	4 years, from May 2015 to April 2019
CONSORTIUM	PIN srl (project coordinator), KNAW, CNRS (Huma-Num), King’s College London, Fachhochschule Postdam, INRIA, Trinity College Dublin, CSIC, Austrian Academy of Sciences, SISMELE, CLARIN, CNR, FORTH, MIBACT-ICC, Academy of Athens
EU CONTRIBUTION	EUR 11 999 711
CALL FOR PROPOSAL	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1 – HORIZON 2020
WEBSITE	http://www.parthenos-project.eu/

ACTIVITIES

PARTHENOS is a Horizon 2020 project that aims at strengthening the cohesion of research in the broad sector of humanities, cultural heritage, history, archaeology and related fields through a thematic cluster of European Research Infrastructures, integrating initiatives, e-infrastructures and other world-class infrastructures, building bridges between different, although tightly interrelated, fields. It will achieve this objective through the definition and support of common standards, the coordination of joint activities, the harmonization of policy definition and implementation, and the develop-

ment of pooled services and of shared solutions to same problems. Also, PARTHENOS supports the work of the two main research infrastructures, DARIAH and CLARIN, and as well as various integration projects addressing cultural domains, such as ARIADNE, CENDARI and EHRI. Since the PARTHENOS kick-off meeting, held in Florence in July 2015, the consortium managed to quickly develop an efficient working methodology and plan the work for 2016, in which several conferences and events will be organized, offering the chance to meet important stakeholders.

FACTSHEET	
FULL PROJECT NAME	Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure ON Cultural Heritage
DURATION	4 years, from May 2015 to April 2019
PROJECT COORDINATOR	CNR
CONSORTIUM	27 partners from 14 countries
EU CONTRIBUTION	EUR 7 994 987,73
CALL FOR PROPOSAL	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015 – HORIZON 2020
WEBSITE	http://www.iperionch.eu/

ACTIVITIES

Iperion CH is a Horizon 2020 funded project which takes up the challenge outlined in the Horizon 2020 – Work Programme 2014-2015 for European research infrastructures, which calls for the establishment of a unique European research infrastructure for restoration and conservation of Cultural Heritage. The project is the follow-on project to the DARIAH affiliated heritage science cluster CHARISMA, which brought together various scientific infrastructures to support the analysis and preservation

of heritage objects. Several methods are used to explore the bulk, microscopic and surface properties of artifacts, including both traditional and advanced analytical techniques. The artworks studied include paintings, sculptures, metal works, ceramics, manuscripts, printed books, archaeological items, and others. Heritage science is an increasingly important interdisciplinary field. The consortium is led by CNR (Scientific Coordinator, Luca Pezzati).

CENDARI

FACTSHEET	
FULL PROJECT NAME	Collaborative European Digital Archival Research Infrastructure
DURATION	4 years, from February 2012 to January 2016
PROJECT COORDINATOR	Trinity College Dublin
CONSORTIUM	Trinity College Dublin (project coordinator), Freie Universität Berlin, University of Birmingham, Czech National Library, Università di Cassino, The European Library, Consortium of European Research Libraries (CERL), King's College, London, INRIA, University of Stuttgart, Goettingen State and University Library, Mathematical Institute of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Fondazione Ezio Franceschini, SISMEI
EU CONTRIBUTION	EUR 6 500 000
CALL FOR PROPOSAL	FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2011-1 – 7 th Framework Programme
WEBSITE	http://www.cendari.eu/

ACTIVITIES

CENDARI was a four-year collaborative integrating activity, which was led by Trinity College Dublin. The project commenced in February 2012 and ended in January 2016.

The final result of the CENDARI project was an integrated research infrastructure offering historical researchers a number of services to access and research dispersed digital archival collections within the two pilot areas of the First World War and medieval European culture. The project produced a digital research infrastructure that is easy to use and access and will be essential to the research goals of the users. The virtual research environment allows for effective knowledge sharing and collaboration between users, for the production of world-class research outputs. On 14 January 2016, the project was launched in Berlin at the Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities. CENDARI's work has resulted in 3 research tools:

- The Archival Directory, which is a large database of archival descriptions and collections. It has a strong transnational focus and one of its aims is to include archives and institutions which are little known or rarely used by researchers.
- The virtual working spaces allow scholars to access historical resources across institutional and national boundaries. The core resources of the working spaces are the Note-Taking Environment, as well as the advanced search functionality. These tools are integrated within the virtual research infrastructure.
- Thematic archival research guides, which are introductory guides to archival material, structured around either one or many archival collections. Their main targets are early career researchers or historians who are starting new research projects.

EHRI

FACTSHEET	
FULL PROJECT NAME	European Holocaust Research Infrastructure
DURATION	4 years, from May 2015 to April 2019
CONSORTIUM	KNAW (project coordinator), CEGESOMA, Jewish Museum in Prague, Institute for Contemporary History in Munich, King’s College London, Yad Vashem, United States Holocaust Memorial Museum, Bundesarchiv, The Wiener Library, International Tracing Service, Emanuel Ringelblum Jewish Historical Institute, Shoah Memorial, Wiener Wiesenthal Institute for Holocaust Studies, Ontotext, Elie Wiesel National Institute for the Study of the Holocaust in Romania, Hungarian Jewish Archives, INRIA, Vilna Gaon State Jewish Museum, Holocaust Documentation Center, Polish Center for Holocaust Research Association, CDEC, Jewish Museum of Greece.
EU CONTRIBUTION	EUR 7 969 673,75
CALL FOR PROPOSAL	H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015 – HORIZON 2020
WEBSITE	http://www.ehri-project.eu/

ACTIVITIES

The European Holocaust Research Infrastructure (**EHRI**) aims to support and facilitate research into the Holocaust by integrating dispersed Holocaust collections and streamlining the access to them. 2015 has been a turning point for the project. The EHRI portal (<https://portal.ehri-project.eu>) was officially launched during the Presentation of the European Holocaust Research Infrastructure on 26 March 2015 in Berlin. The EHRI Portal offers access to in-depth information about Holocaust-related archival institutions and their collection. Furthermore, the European Union has decided to support

the second wave of the EHRI work through 8 million euro of funding under Horizon 2020, which will help sustain and expand its current work. The second phase started in May 2015. EHRI will expand to other countries with a new consortium, enabling the project to reach regions where valuable source material is located, but where access has been rather problematic. Moreover, EHRI will continue its training programme, a refined fellowship programme, and will organize more workshops, conferences, seminars and online courses.

RI Train

FACTSHEET	
FULL PROJECT NAME	Research Infrastructures Training Programme
DURATION	4 years, from September 2015 to August 2019
CONSORTIUM	BBMRI-ERIC (project coordinator), EMBL-EBI, Medical University of Vienna, INFRAFRONTIER GMBH, EATRIS,-ERIC, ECRIN-ERIC, Universidade do Minho, Institute of Molecular Genetics, Imperial College, University of Milano-Bicocca, CNRS, SHARE-ERIC
EU CONTRIBUTION	EUR 1 995 633,75
CALL FOR PROPOSAL	H2020-INFRA supp-2014-2 – HORIZON 2020
WEBSITE	http://ritrain.eu/home

ACTIVITIES

There is a greater need for skilled managers and operators of research infrastructure (RI). Europe must develop the workforce that will turn ~50 nascent RIs with sites in different countries into powerhouses of support for major projects. RItrain will develop a flagship training programme enabling RIs across all domains to gain expertise on governance, organisation, financial and staff management, funding, IP, service provision and outreach in an international context. The project will define competencies required by RIs through consultation with their senior managers. The resulting competency framework will underpin a Bologna-compliant degree, the

Master in Research Infrastructure Management, with three delivery routes. (1) Professionals working in RIs (or organisations representing them) can dip into the content, focusing on areas where there is most need. (2) Management teams can take the course as an organisation, dividing modules between them to gain a certificate for the RI. This will flag the RI as an organisation that values staff development, improving its attractiveness as an employer. (3) Recent graduates and others wishing to enhance their employability can take a full master's degree. By the end of the project, a master's curriculum funded through course fees will be delivered.

#dariah Teach

FACTSHEET	
FULL PROJECT NAME	#dariahTeach
CONSORTIUM	Maynooth University (project coordinator) University of Aarhus, Athena Research Center, Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities, Erasmus University Rotterdam, Austrian Academy of Sciences, University of Lausanne and Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics.
EU CONTRIBUTION	EUR 299 290
CALL FOR PROPOSAL	Erasmus + Strategic Partnership Grant
WEBSITE	http://dariah.eu/teach/

ACTIVITIES

#dariahTeach is a project funded through an Erasmus + Strategic Partnership Grant, which began in January 2015 and runs through June 2017. Its goal is to develop online, open-source, high-quality, multilingual teaching materials for the digital arts and humanities. It also strengthens alliances and fosters innovative teaching and learning practices among members of the DARIAH network, under the lead of Maynooth University, with seven other participating institutions from seven countries (Austria, Denmark, Greece, Ireland, Netherlands, Serbia and Switzerland).

The #dariahTeach website provides details of the project’s public activities in 2015 , which included a poster at DH2015 in July, a presentation at the DARIAH-IE launch event in May, and a collaborative DARIAH Open Humanities Workshop in Belgrade in November. The first year of the project has seen the development of module structure and content based on five prototype modules: Introduction to Digital Humanities, Introduction to TEI, Multimodal Literacies and AV Media, Retrodigitizing Dictionaries and Ontologies. Development of the platform and interaction was based on user requirement work completed by ATHENA R. C. (Greece). The closing event is scheduled for March 2017 in Lausanne.

Annex 6: Financial Summary for 2015

Headline Figures for 2015

Income DARIAH ERIC 2015

Cash Contributions from 15 DARIAH Member Countries

Total: EUR 613,020

Balance 2014: EUR 150,034

Total income: EUR 763,054

Expenditure DARIAH ERIC 2015

Personnel Costs: EUR 348,176

Operating Costs: EUR 17,022

DARIAH Theme: EUR 45,000

Total: EUR 410,198

Balance 2015: EUR 352,857

External Funding

Income

HaS-DARIAH: EUR 868,563

EUROPEANA DSI: EUR 14,927

Expenditure HaS 2015

Personal Costs: EUR 10,844

Prefinancing linked third parties: EUR 466,038

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